

THE IMPORTANCE OF MASSAGE IN THE TREATMENT OF CHILDREN'S DISEASES.

Dustova Gulzoda Komiljonovna

Department of Public Health and health management,
Samarkand State Medical University

Ismatillaeva Rukhshona Bakhrilloyevna

Samarkand State Medical University Vocational Education
course 4th year student

Abstract. Our people are considered a childlike people. The child is not looking at the hardship, and somewhere they quickly switch to taking medicine for pain. But do not feel that the benefits of one member of usable drugs are harmful to the other member. Rickets disease and flatfoot are now common in children. When a baby has been diagnosed with dysplasia, oblique neck, flatulence, congenital defects in the pelvic bones, rubbing is the best treatment measure. When most newborns experience neurological disorders such as hypertonus, problems in the flexion of the legs and fingers, curative ugliness is recommended by the pediatrician, and we must not forget that such procedures should be carried out by a nursing nurse.

Key words: children, disease, massage

The purpose of the study: to treat diseases that occur in children with the methods of physiotherapy and to carry out prevention to prevent diseases. Treat children's health not with medication, but with harmless methods in folk medicine.

Materials and methods: Works of Chinese folk medicine, works of Abu Ali Ibn Sino and the enslavement of physiotherapy methods, articles on the totality of methods of treatment in folk medicine in children were used.

Result and discussion: Several methods of Physiotherapy differ. These include, for example, massage, electrophoresis, paraffin, hydrotherapy, gerudotherapy, manual therapy, balneo Therapy, Healing Body Training, Phytotherapy, acupuncture, akupressura, etc. Of these, such as massage, electrophoresis, paraffin, physical education, hydrotherapy are used in children. The

most commonly used physiotherapy method is massage, when flat footedness, oblique neck, pelvic protrusions are observed, which occurs in children. Before massaging the baby, mothers should take into account the anatomic-physiological characteristics of the child's body. For example extremely sensitive areas-the adrenal (right rib tag) and genitals, the nipples are not massaged. Since a lot of nerve fibers are located on the inner side of the pelvic area, it is better not to rub this area. When a child is crying, starving in the abdomen or when somewhere hurts, as well as there are purulent lesions on the baby's skin, it cannot be upped in cases of birth with heart failure or when the liver is enlarged due to illness. The massage treatment is suspended until the body recovers when the temperature rises.

Let the room to be massaged be bright, clean, warm, without windshield, air temperature range +22-25C. Choose the most comfortable place in the house for massage. It can be a sofa, bed, table top. You can put on soft music. Place one, two smaller toys that the child likes best in front of him. You can start massaging 30 - 40 minutes after the child has eaten. Let the baby's skin be clean and dry during the massage. Make an oil or cream that is suitable for his skin. Undress the child and lay him in the prepared place. He should be in a good mood so that he is not bothered by the massage. Lubricate your hands and warm up by rubbing so that your fingers can move lightly on the baby's body while you rub. Because the baby should not shake and feel warmth. Lightly gently rub his face and throat with your fingertips. Gently move the chest, eyebrow spacing towards the chin. Massage your ears slowly, as if drawing your nose and lip, and then. Gently rub the baby's abdominal

area with a circular motion in a careful clockwise direction. When rubbing the chest area, gently rub with your fingertips in a movement that starts from the middle at the junction of the rib and goes under the armpits. Let your fingers move gently and lightly, from center to side. Hold the tip of the leg, lift it up and rub it from the outside, from the bottom up, towards the pelvis. Remember that it is extremely important to rub the soles of the feet, paws. Lightly rub the foot on top and bottom. Rub each finger with the tag separately. Turn the baby to the belly and rub the back from the neck to the buttocks and from the buttocks to the neck. It is impossible to nourish the spine itself. Keep an eye on the baby's skin during treatment. It is not good for the skin to become very red, bruise or feel pain and cry. Prophylactic massage lasts 4-7 minutes 3-4 times a day, while curative massage is done 15 minutes once a day.

Conclusion: in the treatment of diseases in many children, parents in a hurry use medication for children to quickly eliminate the disease, taking into account the fact that any drug preparations have a detrimental effect on the body, as well as their beneficial side, taking into account the fact that from the beginning of the disease they naturally increase the child's immunity, Against the background of each disease lies a violation of cell activity, the metabolism of substances is accelerated due to the improvement of blood circulation through a simple massage, the function of the cell is improved due to the improvement of metabolism in cells. The body itself is considered an internal healer, has the property of self-healing is considered sufficient only if it helps him a little from the external environment. For this, it is advisable to do not drug from the outside, but natural herbs, physiotherapeutic procedures that improve the metabolism.

REFERENCES

1. Dustova G., Soxiba I. TIBBIYOT OLIY O 'QUV YURTLARIDA SOG 'LOM TURMUSH TARZI HAQIDA TA'LIM BERISHNING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 754-759.

2. Dustova G. K. et al. Measures taken to prevent coronavirus infection in Samarkand region //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 11 (78). – С. 102-105.
3. Dustova G. K., Kurbanov A. A. SAMARQAND VILOYATI AHOLISI ORASIDA COVID-19 KASALLIGIDAN KEYINGI BEMORLARGA KUZATILGAN KASALLIKNING ASORATI VA KASALLIKLARNING O’ZIGA XOS KECHISH XUSUSIYATLARI //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 186-189.
4. Ergashevna K. D. et al. The Level and Structure of the Incidence of Malignant Tumors of the Oral Cavity Among the Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan //International Journal on Integrated Education. – Т. 3. – №. 12. – С. 177-180.
5. Ergashevna, K. D., Komildzhonovna, D. G., Khakimovna, K. K., & Rahmatulloevich, K. K. The Level and Structure of the Incidence of Malignant Tumors of the Oral Cavity Among the Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(12), 177-180.
6. Dustova G. K., O’rinboyev F. X. O’ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA TIBBIY SUG’URTANI JORIY ETISH BEMORLAR SOG’LIG’INI TIKLASH UCHUN ILK QADAM SIFATIDA //Involta Scientific Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 41-45.
7. Kurbanov Anvar A’lamovich, & Dustova Gulzoda Komiljanovna. (2023). AHOLI O’RTASIDA YUQUMLI KASALLIKLARNING KELIB CHIQISHI VA TARQALISHI XAVFINI KUCHAYTIRUVCHI OMILLAR. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 5(1), 9–12. Retrieved from <http://web-journal.ru/index.php/journal/article/view/520>
8. A’lamovich K. A., Komiljanovna D. G. AHOLI O’RTASIDA YUQUMLI KASALLIKLARNING KELIB CHIQISHI VA TARQALISHI XAVFINI KUCHAYTIRUVCHI OMILLAR //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 9-12.
9. Gulzoda Komiljanovna Dustova, Ruxshona Baxrillayevna Ismatullayeva ABU RAYHON BERUNIYNING “SAYDANA” ASARINING XUSUSIYATLARI //

Academic research in educational sciences. 2022. №3. URL:

<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/abu-rayhon-beruniyning-saydana-asarining->

xususiyatlari (дата обращения: 24.01.2024).